

Germplasm improvement

Genetics

Genetic variability in floral traits of 10 cyto sterile lines of rice (*Oryza sativa* L.)

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We evaluated 10 cyto sterile lines and their respective maintainers for different floral traits such as duration of opening of florets, angle of opened florets, percentage of stigma exertion, percentage of panicle exertion, stigma length, anther length, filament length,

and stigma surface influencing outcrossing in rice. Results are shown in the table.

Analysis of variance recorded highly significant treatment differences for all traits, indicating the presence of variability for selection. Some of the most important floral traits—duration of opening of florets, angle of opened florets, percentage of stigma exertion, and percentage of panicle exertion—substantially influencing outcrossing—were predominant in cyto sterile lines PMS2A/B, PMS6A/B, PMS7A/B, IR58025A/B, and IR62829A/B.

On the basis of variability studies, cyto sterile line IR62829A/B expressed the best values overall for stigma characteristics (stigma exertion percentage, stigma length, stigma surface) followed by PMS3A/B, PMS10A/B, and PMS2A/B. The most popular CMS line, IR58025A, showed poorer stigma characteristics compared with other cyto sterile lines, but it had pronounced anther characteristics. In general, A lines showed better traits that influence outcrossing than their respective B lines. ■

Analysis of variance and genetic parameters of variation and mean performance for eight floral characters in 10 cyto sterile lines (A) and their maintainer lines (B) in rice.^a

Source	df	DOF (min)		PSE		PPE		AOF (O°)		SL (mm)		SS (mm ²)		AL (mm)		FL (mm)	
		A/B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	
<i>Analysis of variance</i>																	
Replication	2	775.61	62.50	13.03	9.85	2.58	10.51	2.36	0.40	0.008	0.009	0.018	0.007	0.013	0.009	0.002	0.037
Treatment (G)	9	2,420.98**	378.79**	399.03**	264.83**	70.49**	236.65**	23.32**	17.86**	0.154**	0.172**	0.042**	0.067**	0.037*	0.065**	0.078**	0.114**
Error	18	288.22	76.15	11.75	5.65	2.99	6.37	2.50	2.58	0.008	0.008	0.005	0.010	0.011	0.011	0.023	0.044
CD (5%)	-	29.12	14.95	5.86	4.68	2.96	4.33	2.75	2.75	0.153	0.157	0.119	0.170	0.185	0.183	0.260	0.359
<i>Genetic parameters of variation</i>																	
Mean		90.57	64.50	50.92	53.26	64.63	90.04	25.26	23.07	1.42	1.43	0.61	0.62	1.89	1.95	1.06	1.28
CV (%)		18.33	13.53	7.60	8.42	3.14	3.43	6.34	6.96	6.27	6.47	11.40	16.06	5.73	5.47	14.28	16.33
Range (minimum)		61.67	47.50	7.88	29.45	58.45	77.90	22.89	19.67	1.19	1.19	0.47	0.45	1.72	1.72	0.79	1.17
Range (maximum)		146.67	84.17	66.71	75.19	69.01	100.00	32.45	27.61	1.97	2.02	0.80	0.94	2.04	2.19	1.33	1.53
Variance (P)		2,613.13	429.56	371.60	275.26	72.48	240.89	25.00	19.58	0.16	0.18	0.045	0.07	0.44	0.08	0.09	0.14
Variance (G)		2,324.90	353.41	359.85	259.61	69.49	234.52	22.47	17.00	0.15	0.17	0.040	0.06	0.03	0.06	0.07	0.01
Coefficient (PCV)		34.14	20.63	26.32	21.13	9.17	12.38	12.20	12.00	16.81	17.60	21.59	27.49	7.49	8.74	19.09	20.24
Variance (GCV)		28.80	28.80	25.20	25.20	8.42	8.42	10.42	9.77	15.59	16.36	18.33	22.31	4.83	6.82	12.67	11.96
<i>Mean performance</i>																	
IR58025A/B		103.06	71.67	53.28	56.93	68.96	85.21	24.00	22.89	1.23	1.19	0.47	0.45	1.80	1.82	1.10	1.17
IR62829A/B		72.33	70.00	65.61	71.07	66.22	89.78	27.00	25.77	1.97	2.02	0.80	0.94	1.79	2.19	1.01	1.50
PMS2A/B		146.67	50.83	49.83	42.49	66.45	89.15	24.11	20.88	1.28	1.33	0.49	0.53	1.84	1.86	0.92	1.41
PMS3A/B		71.50	47.50	38.54	50.94	64.65	77.90	23.78	24.00	1.42	1.43	0.71	0.65	1.97	2.00	0.94	1.53
PMS6A/B		131.67	84.17	66.71	59.34	61.03	100.00	24.67	20.88	1.37	1.38	0.49	0.48	1.72	1.72	1.23	1.31
PMS7A/B		105.00	68.33	56.43	48.47	65.43	93.60	32.45	27.67	1.26	1.26	0.51	0.50	2.04	2.12	1.09	1.20
PMS8A/B		61.67	58.33	65.15	75.19	58.45	93.55	24.44	22.00	1.47	1.47	0.60	0.62	1.82	1.83	0.79	0.88
PMS10A/B		84.17	64.17	48.37	67.35	62.03	86.48	23.44	19.67	1.43	1.44	0.67	0.68	2.00	2.05	1.33	1.42
NMS1A/B		70.55	56.67	57.43	29.45	69.01	99.32	25.78	24.45	1.55	1.54	0.61	0.57	2.00	2.03	1.06	1.22
NMS2A/B		79.17	73.33	7.88	31.39	62.02	85.39	22.89	22.78	1.19	1.20	0.75	0.76	1.93	1.94	1.21	1.17

** = significant at 1% level, * = significant at 5% level, GCV = genotypic coefficient of variation, PCV = phenotypic coefficient of variation, DOF = duration of opening of florets, PSE = percentage of stigma exertion, PPE = percentage of panicle exertion, AOF = angle of opened florets, SL = stigma length, SS = stigma surface, AL = anther length, FL = filament length.